

MANAGEMENT OF MANYASTAMBHA WITH BRUHAT PANCHAMOOLA KWATH NASYA AND STHANIK RUKSHA SWEDAN (VALUKA POTTALI) A CASE STUDY

*¹Dr. Krutika Laxman Janathe, ²Dr. Kalpana Gholap

India.

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***Corresponding Author**

Dr. Krutika Laxman Janathe

India.

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ABSTRACT

Ancient societies relied on Physical labour for survival, which often resulted in higher levels of Physical fitness. Diets were generally based on locally sourced and whole foods, with limited access to technology. Today is the era of modernization and fast life, sedentary and stressful life, changing lifestyles result in experiencing many imbalances in their biological system. In today's era, Manyastambha is the most common disorder. Manyastambha has been described as Vataja Nanatmaja vikara.^[1] Aacharaya Sushruta has explained Manyastambha with its treatment in a detailed manner. The Manyastambha word is derived from words as "Manya," which means the nape of the neck, and "Stambha," which means stiffness. Manyastambha is UrdhWajatrugata roga. The standard Ayurvedic approach for this condition includes Ruksha sWedan (Dry fomentation) and Nasya karma (nasal administration of

medicine). This study evaluates the combined efficacy of Bruhat panchamoola kWath Nasya and Ruksha sWedan in the management of Manyastambha.^[2]

KEYWORDS: Manyastambh, Nasya, Ruksha sWedan, Panchkarma, UrdhWajatrugat vyadhi.

INTRODUCTION

People are predisposed to various diseases based on their way of living and occupational habits. People face so many health issues like Back pain, Neck pain, Body ache, Knee joint pain, Affects Vision, Headache, etc. The main factors contributing to the lifestyle include

unhealthy food, no exercise, wrong body postures/ wrong sitting positions, and long hours working on computers.

Manyastambha is the stiffness of the neck. The etiological factors responsible for the Manyastambha are sleeping during the daytime, irregular postures or leaning on an uneven place, and constantly gazing upwards.^[3] As mentioned in Sushruta Samhita, sleeping during the day, wrong body postures, wrong sitting positions, staring at one point for a long period, cause vitiation of Vata Dosha and Kapha Dosha Avarana. Due to Nidana sevana, Vata gets vitiated and gets Kapha avrutta, which in turn does stambha of 14 Manya Siras situated in the back of the Neck and results in Manyastambha. Pain and Stiffness are the cardinal signs of the Manyastambha.

The treatment available for Neck pain, according to Modern medicine, is mostly the use of painkillers and steroids. However, this is just a temporary solution. Pain reoccurs after the effect of the medicine subsides, and eventually, the patient becomes dependent on this treatment. Manyastambha is UrdhWajatrugat vyadhi.^[4] As we all know, the general line of treatment for Manyastambha mentioned in Sushruta Samhita is Nasya karma and Ruksha sWedan karma.^[5] “Nasashi Shiraso DWaram.”^[6,7,8] i.e., Nasa is told as DWara for Shiras, which is Uttamanga. Nasya is considered the prime modality of treatment in UrdhWajatrugata Vikaras. It has an important action in clearing the Doshas that are deep-rooted in the channels of the head.

In this study, daily freshly prepared Bruhat panchamool kwath for Nasya karma and Ruksha sWedan (Valuka pottali) will be taken for the management of Manyastambha. Bruhat panchamool kwath for Nasya karma, as it has Vatakaphagna properties, it mitigates Vata with the help of its Rasa, Guna, Virya, Vipaka, and Doshaghanata.

Nasya reverses the effects of Kapha Avarana, which is mainly involved in the pathogenesis of Manyastambha. For Ruksha sWedan karma, Valuka pottali will be taken because it is easily available and affordable. Ruksha sWedan Karma helps to relieve Pain, Stiffness, and Relaxation of muscles. So, as mentioned in Sushruta Samhita, Nasya karma and Ruksha sWedan karma are effective in the management of Manyastambha.

CASE PRESENTATION**Vartaman vedana with kaal (Present complaints)**

An IT Engineer, aged 40 years, reported to the OPD, with main complaints of Pain and stiffness in the cervical region (Manya Pradesh), restricted movements of the cervical region since 2-3 months.

Vedana vruttanta (H/O present illness)

The patient was well before 3 months, then started complaining of pain in the neck, later developed stiffness in the neck region, and had restricted movements of the neck. He took allopathic medicine for the same and got some temporary relief in pain, stiffness, and restricted movements, but for the last 2 months, the condition has been affecting his day-to-day activities.

Purva vyadhi vruttanta (H/O Past illness)

No H/O DM, HTN, or any other major illness.

Purva chikitsa vruttanta (pre-medical history)

The patient was treated for the above-mentioned condition with allopathic medicine, which gave him temporary relief.

Samanya pariksha

Physical examination	Systemic examination
BP – 120/90 mmhg	RS: AEBE clear
Weight – 72.8 kg	CVS: S1S2 (N)
Height – 167 cm	CNS: Conscious, oriented
Temp - Afebrile	

Ashtavidha pariksha

Nadi: 76/ min Mala: prakruta Mutra: prakruta Jiwha : nirama Shabda: spashta

Sparsha: anushnashita Drik: prakruta

Aakruti: Madhyama

Dashvidha pariksha :

Prakruti: vaatkapha

Vikruti: dosha- vaatpradhan kaphaanubandha Upadhatu: sira, snayu

Sara: madhyama Samhanana: madhyama Pramana: madhyama Satmya: madyama Satwa: madhyama Aharshakti: madhyama

Vyayamshakti: madhyama Vaya: madhyama

Samprapti ghatakas

Dosha: Vata – Vyana; kapha – shleshmakapha Dushya: rasa, asthi, majja, sira, snayu

Strotas: asthivaha, mamasavaha Strotodushtiprakara: sanga

Udbhavsthana: siras of manya pradesha (cervical region) Sancharsthana: sira

Vyaktasthana: Manya Pradesh (cervical region) Adhishthana: manya Pradesh

Rogmarga: madhyama Vyadhiswabhava: sadhya

Vyadhi Vyavachedaka Nidan:

- 1] *Avabahuka*: *Vitiated Vata* when it gets lodged in *bahushira* causes *Avabahuka*, described by *Acharya Bhavprakash*. The symptom of inability to lift the hand is described in *Apabahuka*, but it is not observed in this condition.
- 2] *VishWachi*: *Acharya Sushruta* explains *VishWachi* as that which causes *Karmakshaya* of *bahu* due to the *dushti* of *kandara*, which runs from *bahu prasta* towards *talabhaga* of *hasta* and *angulis*. The symptoms are pain, stiffness, loss of function, and difficulty in movements of the hand, but it is not observed in this condition.

Vyadhi Vinishchhaya

Pain over the back of the neck and head, along with restricted movements and stiffness, indicates the diagnosis of *Manyastambha*.

Roga pariksha

Nidana^[9,10] long hours of work on computers, improper postures, sleeping using high and hard pillows, *diWasWapna*

Poorva Roopa^[11] The Purvarupa manifests in the *Shanasanshraya Avastha* of *Shadkriyakala*. There is no separate explanation in the classics about the *Purvarupa* of *Manyastambha*. "*Avyaktam Lakshanam Tesham Purvarupam Iti Smritam*"

Roopa^[12]: *shoola* and *stambha* in *manyapradesh*

Upashaya: *swedana*

Anupashaya: *diwaswapana*, *katu amla lavana ahar*, *abhishyandiahara*

Samprapriti

Excessive consumption or / exposure to the etiological factors leading to excessive aggravation of kapha and partial imbalance of vata

The doshas move towards manya, the back of the neck/nape of the neck, and get lodged therein

Kapha envelops and blocks the vata

The normal functioning of vata is disturbed

There occurs pain, loss of movement, and tilting of the neck due to the affliction of nerves, muscles, tendons, and soft tissues in the nape of the neck

Manyastambha

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ayurvedic literature included samhitas, and research articles were used as source material.

Type of study:- Single-arm clinical trial.

Intervention:- a) Ruksha swedan (15-20min) upto Samyak svinna lakshan

b) Bruhat panchamool kwath nasya (avapida nasya) 6* / 6*

Follow up :- follow up assessment criteria on day 0,7th,14th day

Drug review

Drug	rasa	guna	veerya	vipaka	Dosha karma	action
Bilva ^[13]	Kashaya, Tikta	Laghu, Ruksha	Ushna	Katu	Kaphavatasha mak	Shothahara, Vedanasthapana
Agnimanth ^[14]	Tikta, Katu, Kashaya, Madhura	Ruksha, Laghu	Ushna	Katu	Kaphavatasha mak	Shothahara, Vedanasthapana
Shyonak ^[15]	Madhura, Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu, Ruksha	Ushna	Katu	Kaphavatasha mak	Shothahara, Vedanasthapana
Patala ^[16]	Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu, Ruksha	Ushna	Katu	Kaphavatasha mak	Shothahara, Vedanasthapana
Gambhari ^[17]	Tikta, Kashaya, Madhura	Guru	Ushna	Katu	tridoshashamaka	Shothahara, Vedanasthapana

Chikitsa Siddhanta

The general line of treatment of *manyastambha* is *nasya* and *ruksha sWeda*.^[18]

Ruksha swedan (valuka pottali)

Bruhat panchamoola kwath nasya

Method of Valuka Swedana

Ask the patient to lie in the prone position on a *droni*.

The hot *valukapottali* should be applied over *manya pradesh*.

The *pottalis* should be used alternatively after reheating to maintain uniform temperature throughout the procedure.

It should be done for about 15-20 minutes.

Remove the *pottali* and gently wipe the treated area with a soft, clean towel. Avoid vigorous rubbing.

Method of Nasya karma

The patient was asked to lie down comfortably in the supine position on the procedure table.

Sthanik snehan done on face, temporal region, neck region, nose with lukewarm tila taila.

After abhyanga, *sthanik mrudu sWedana* is done by covering the eyes with wet cotton.

The head part was made to extend further from the edge of the table, bending at an angle of 45°, making it a low head position.

6-6 *bindu* of kwatha was administered in each nostril.

After nasal administration, the patient was allowed to relax in the supine position.

Patient advised to spit out the nasal secretions reaching the throat.

Dhoompana

Gandusha with *koshna jal* given.

Patient advised to follow *nidan parivarjana*, like avoiding cold water for bathing and drinking.

Stages		
Vitals		Vitals taken before procedure. Bp, pulse, rr, temp taken.
Procedure	Purva karma ^[19]	Sthanik abhyanga with tila taila Sthanik Mrudu Swadna
	Pradhan karma ^[20]	Administered kwath in the nostrils Drug: Bruhat Panchamoola Kwath Dose: 6-6 bindu
	Pacchat karma ^[21]	spit out the nasal secretions dhoompana gandusha
Duration of treatment		7 days
Duration of study		14 days

Results of treatment

- Pain and stiffness in the neck were reduced.
- Normal movements of the neck without pain.

SN	Laxanas	B.T. (Day 0)	A.T.(Day 7)	F.U.(Day 14)
1	Manyashoola	8	0	0
2	Manyastambha	3	0	0
3	Flexion	30°	80°	80°
4	Extension	40°	70°	70°
5	Lateral flexion	Right	20°	45°
		Left	20°	45°
6	Rotation	Right	40°	90°
		Left	50°	90°

DISCUSSION

Mode of action of ruksha swedana.

Pacifying vata and kapha doshas (Ayurvedic perspective)

Manyastambha is a *vata kapha vyadhi*. *Valuka sWedana*, being a *ruksha* (dry) and *ushna* (hot) procedure, is effective for pacifying both aggravated *vata* and *kapha* doshas.

As *sWedan* procedure, its classical action is to relieve *stambha*(stiffness), *guarava* (heaviness), *sheeta* (coldness).

This procedure helps in *strotoshodhana*, which further subsides the vitiated *doshas* and related symptoms.

Physiological effects (modern perspective)

Improves blood circulation: the heat causes vasodilatation (expansion of blood vessels),

which improves blood flow to the affected cervical, thereby restoring vital nutrients and oxygen.

Removes toxins: Aids in the elimination of toxins and metabolic wastes. Analgesic effect: Provides an analgesic (pain-relieving) effect at the cellular level. The application of therapeutic heat stimulates local neural receptors, which may help to modulate the pain signals (Ruk) through mechanisms like the gate-control theory of pain.

Relieving stiffness

Increasing mobility – by reducing stiffness and relaxing the muscles, the therapy helps to increase the range of motion of the neck.

Mode of action of kwath nasya

Nasa is mentioned as a gateway to *Shira*, and diseases that affect the *Shira* can be cured by *Nasya*. *Manyastambha* is *shleshmanavrutta vata vyadhi*. *Nasya* is the best line of treatment for *manyastambha*. *Bruhat panchamoola kwath nasya* breaks the pathology of the diseases, gives strength to the neck region, and improves neck movements.

Clearing obstruction: in *manyastambha*, where *kapha* has obstructed (*avarana*) the path of *vata*, the *ushna* and *vata-kaphahara* properties of *kWath* help to break this pathology, allowing *vata* to move freely.

Tissue nourishment: it nourishes the depleted tissues (*dhatu*s), such as the bone (*asthi*) and muscles (*mamsa*), thereby relieving stiffness.

Local impact: the nasal route ensures a localised, high concentration of the medicine reaches the affected *sira* (*vessels*), *snayus* (*ligaments*), and *kandara* (*tendons*), leading to reduced spasm and increased range of motion of the neck.

CONCLUSION

Bruhat panchamoola kWath nasya is effective in *shleshmanavrutta vata* condition.

Bruat panchamoola kWath nasya can be used for 7 days continuously for a significant effect in *manyastambha*.

The reduction in cardinal signs of *manyastambha*, i.e., pain and stiffness and also increases the range of motion of the neck.

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